

Grant 730895, ReIReS

Deliverable 6.1 Requirements Overview and Use Case Models

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1. Document Overview

1.1. Objective

The objective of task 6.1 is to identify the functional and non-functional requirements of the different stakeholders in the ReIReS consortium with regard to the resource discovery platform on religious history, which itself is the objective of Work Package 6. There exist already many digital resources and databases in this field. These are, however, still dispersed and the datasets are organized along various data models, which hinders the interoperability of all these resources related to religious studies. WP6 therefore aims to enhance the discoverability of data, regardless of location, metadata models, classifications and language while also improving visibility for public and commercial database providers.

The first task and deliverable in this work package relates to the first steps generally taken in the creation of a data repository and discovery system: requirements analysis and use case models. The requirements analysis involves collecting input from the relevant data providers and researchers from the partner organizations regarding the needs and conditions that the unified data repository and discovery system must meet. User stories, the first step in collecting input, represent requirements told from the perspective of potential users to show the needs of future users. This helps to identify potential requirements the proposed platform needs to adhere to for it to become an instrument for resource discovery and linking for religious studies.

A survey pertaining to the datasets already managed by the ReIReS partner institutions was also sent out to develop an overview of their potential interoperability on technical and metadata level. This is partly preparation for Task 6.2. (Metadata & ontology modeling), but in 6.1. serves to motivate the selection of datasets to be included in a pilot project of the unified repository and discovery system to be built on and to build on the requirements overview and use case models.

1.2. Scope

The first section will outline the dataset survey and subsequent selection of those to be included in the pilot project. A summary of the survey was also provided to WP8 for dissemination on the website.

The second section focuses on use case modelling and the methodology used in this process.

The result of this, a requirements analysis, will be the subject of the third and final main section.

1.3. Applicable Documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

Id.	Date	Title / Reference
[A1]	20/03/2017	H2020-INFRAIA-2016-2017, (Integrating and opening research infrastructures of European interest), Proposal number: 730895-2
[A2]	10/01/2018	GRANT AGREEMENT, NUMBER — 730895 — ReIReS,
[A3]	01/02/2018	DESCA - ReIReS Consortium Agreement
[A4]		
[A5]		
[A6]		

All documents mentioned in this list are available in the Document Repository, section "Applicable Documents".

1.4. Reference Documents

Reference documents are intended to provide background and supplementary information.

Id.	Date	Title / Reference
[R1]		
[R2]		
[R3]		
[R4]		
[R5]		
[R6]		
[R7]		
[R8]		
[R9]		
[R10]		

1.5. Glossary

A glossary of terms and acronyms used in this document is included in Annex 1.

2. Dataset Survey

2.1. Objective

Work Package 6 aims to bring together the numerous digital resources and databases already available in the domain of religious studies, primarily from the public research institutions and commercial publisher involved in the ReIReS consortium; and potentially from external partners at a later stage. Therefore, from its earliest onset, there needs to be an overview, as complete as possible, of the datasets available throughout the consortium. Neither the functionality of the eventual platform, nor the structure of its data model can be conceived without this overview.

The results of this survey serve to provide insight into the technical interoperability of the datasets managed by the partners. This provided the necessary insight into the technical and organizational aspects of their datasets and made it possible to make a selection of suitable datasets for the pilot project. The summary of the results of this survey are also delivered to WP8, to serve the dissemination of information about the datasets managed by consortium members.

The ReIReS consortium offers a wide range of different datasets ranging from highly standardized bibliographical datasets to diverse research databases following an own model. The ReIReS data model will have to incorporate these different types of information in a single model. This might mean creating a data model that incorporates multiple metadata elements into a single denominator. The challenge will be finding the right balance so that partners are still able to interpret the ReIReS data model and map their datasets to this model, while keeping enough of the semantics to make the data interesting for researchers. While the datamodelling itself is part of task 6.2 and deliverable 6.2 (month 14 – March 2019), a data survey was composed at the very start of the project and sent out to the members of the ReIReS consortium to ascertain who managed relevant datasets and to gather all the necessary information about them. Each partner had to fill out at least one survey form, regardless of them having any digital data to contribute, so as to be sure that the lack of a response could not be interpreted as a lack of relevant data. The partners were asked to fill out a survey for each separate dataset, to account for possible technical and ontological differences between digital repositories inside a single institution and to cover the variety of data as fully as possible.

The ReIReS partners were sent a preparation document containing introductory remarks and the contents of the actual data survey.¹ For completion of the survey, they were directed to an online survey form, which facilitated the extraction of the results into a clear and interpretable format.² The online survey was conducted with the help of Zoho Forms, an online application made by the Zoho Corporation for the creation and sharing of online forms that ensures the data is handled securely.³ Besides some general information,

¹ See Annex 1. Preparation document data survey

² See Annex 2. ReIReS WP6 Data Survey Form for an example

³ <https://www.zoho.com/forms>

the survey focused on contact data for those responsible for the datasets, access information, technical details, and data models and interoperability.

Based on that information, further analysis involved contacting the different data specialists and technical people to discuss their datasets, used data models and technical exchange options in further detail.

The contact information provided in the survey also served as a basis for the creation of a WP6 mailing list. Individuals mentioned in the forms were asked if they wanted to subscribe and whether or not other people would be interested. During the course of the project, other interested people were added to the mailing list sporadically.

WP6 will look at best practices and lessons learned from previous projects bringing a wide variety of data together (e.g. Europeana, CLARIN, ...).⁴ It will also look at the more recent advances in data modeling such as ontologies, which can consist of different layers of complexity.

2.2. Results

It was possible to review the existing platforms from partners and use that as inspiration for the unified discovery platform based on the survey results. The results were therefore analyzed and served as a stepping-stone for the process of use case modelling and requirements analysis. The different models for metadata and their applications will serve as the foundation for the definition of a common metadata model for the ReIReS unified data repository and discovery system. The disparate datasets require the creation of a network of interlinked classifications and multilingual vocabularies for the semantic enrichment of the datasets in order to be searchable in a single user interface.

There are two possible paths for linking these different datasets together into one search platform.

- **Aggregated search model:** Data from different providers is imported into a central database after mapping and normalizing the metadata. The metadata is presented consistently, but it is also duplicated.
- **Federated search model:** Users are able to query the data of different repositories without the need to import the records into a central database. Although this is more flexible and does not require duplication, it is only feasible if the data provider has the necessary API's in place to provide live access.

The results of the survey showed that only a minority of datasets are viable for a federated search model and some could be, considering the willingness of the data provider to develop the necessary API. Most of the remaining datasets will have to be exported by the data provider, mapped to a common metadata standard and imported into the ReIReS data repository.

⁴ <https://www.clarin.eu/>

<https://www.europeana.eu/portal/en>

The detailed results of the survey were also summarized in a document that contains no personal information or contact details. This document contained only descriptive information about the datasets and was used for further communication and dissemination.⁵

2.3. Implementation.

A combination of the two aforementioned search models means that implementation becomes much more complex. A pilot project will be necessary, to analyze the possibilities and restrictions faced in building this platform. A few datasets will have to be selected before there can be a finished project that integrates all the relevant datasets managed by the partners in the consortium. Keeping in mind the differences between these datasets, the first phase of this pilot should prioritize at least two disparate datasets, so that both aforementioned search models can be tested.

The feasibility of a second and third phase depend on the time and resources available after the prioritized datasets have been integrated in the pilot project.

During the progression of those phases, priorities might change and the integration of some datasets could be handled in a different phase. Although the consortium agreement only specifies the inclusion of two or three datasets for the pilot project, it could be possible to integrate more datasets further along in the process if time is available. The datasets that have been prioritized focus mainly on bibliographical data, but for the purposes of a pilot project, this is certainly warranted. Eventually it should also be possible to add authority records on people, places, etc. in the data repository.

The selection of prioritized datasets and the motivation of that selection was presented to the Executive Board for review, along with the priorities with which the other datasets might be included during a pilot project. This document was sent to the Executive Board on July 3rd 2018 and is included here as Annex 4. No further input was received on this document.

⁵ <http://reires.eu/datasets/>

3. Use Case Modelling

3.1. Objective

User stories represent requirements told from the perspective of the users and show the added value and needs of the users. In order to develop a unified data repository and discovery platform, information is needed as to who the users will be and to what purpose they will need to use the platform.⁶ Those use cases are to be integrated into a requirement analysis, to further tailor it to the specific needs of this project. It is important to write these user stories while taking into consideration different types of users, to cover the complexity of front-end and back-end requirements that need to be met.

Furthermore, requesting input and feedback from individuals inside the consortium engages them in the development of the platform. It helps manage their expectations regarding the possibilities and limitations of this project. Chances are that partners who have little experience with writing use cases for digital environments will have difficulty in providing input for the requirements analysis phase. The risk is that the discovery service platform of WP6 will not meet the needs of partners, data providers and researchers. WP6 will provide easy to use use case template with some examples to help partners on their way.

3.2. Methodology

Potential respondents were contacted via the ReIReS WP6 mailing list and given the necessary backstory about the methodology and reasoning behind use case modelling, along with instructions on how to write user stories and a template they could use to write them coherently and consistently. The User Story Manual is included here as Annex 4 and the template is included as a part of Annex 5, the results of the survey already integrated in it.

User stories should be described in short simple sentences, stating who wants what and why. In the structure of the template, this was phrased as follows: “As *<a type of user>* I want *<to do something>* so that *<it has a use for me>*”. Respondents were asked to supplement the user stories by filling in the information missing between brackets and possibly add notes or priorities in an Excel spreadsheet.

In creating user stories, the focus should be on a specific main goal, written from the perspective of specific types of users and purposes. It is not necessary to give technical solutions or to mention specific products in these user stories, or to describe the desired solution in detail, as that would limit the investigation of different types of (technical solutions). It is not the intention of user stories to describe the functionality entirely or in detail, but rather for future users to indicate their needs and expectations.

Primarily these user stories serve to supplement the requirements overview and direct the priorities therein, as part of a preliminary investigation into the technical feasibility and potential solutions. However, they can also be reviewed with the partners to further clarify the desired effects of the user stories, to exchange ideas, and to specify potential first priorities.

⁶ For further information on user stories: <https://www.mountaingoatsoftware.com/agile/user-stories>

3.3. Results

Thanks to the input received from these user stories, the expectations of ReIReS partners could be documented and implemented in the requirements of the unified discovery platform.

There was a clear inclination towards the need for user-friendly and efficient search functions. Considering the disparate nature of datasets within the consortium, the different perspectives of the respondents brought multiple aspects of this functionality to light. This allowed for the enhancement of some requirements already specified by the WP6 team and for the inclusion of new ones.

Clearly, respondents were also aware of the benefits of making their datasets interoperable and the potential for metadata enrichment which that implies. From their perspective as collection experts, they emphasized the importance of the standardization and reuse of data. There is a clear indication that respondents hold the expectation that the ReIReS platform could be a discovery infrastructure for both people and machines (e.g. indexing services, other search platforms).

3.4. Implementation

The user stories are converted into requirements and priorities are indicated in cooperation with the ReIReS partners, for which the MoSCoW-method is used. Some respondents gave use cases quite similar to one another, indicating the value placed on the resulting requirements, as well as giving the WP6 team more than one perspective to look at these requirements from. This is a good example of how use cases are implemented, namely by connecting a functionality to a more practical outlook on that functionality. Furthermore, when use cases are included that do not fit the scope of this project, the WP6 team has the opportunity to outline the reasons for not including that functionality beforehand.

Some of these use cases have not been implemented into the requirement document for this deliverable, because they translate into requirements that are related more to the eventual data model. These cases are therefore more relevant to Task 6.2. 'Metadata & ontology modeling'.

4. The MoSCoW method⁷

The MoSCoW method is a prioritization technique used to reach a common understanding with stakeholders on the importance of the fulfillment of each requirement. All requirements are important, but they are prioritized early on in a project to deliver the most benefit.

- **Must have:** These requirements are critical to the project in order for it to be a success. Even if one of these is not included, the project delivery could be considered a failure. However, requirements can be downgraded from *Must have* if all relevant stakeholders agree to this, when new requirements are deemed more important.
- **Should have:** Requirements with this label are important, but not necessary. While they can be as important as *Must have*, they are often not as time-critical or there may be another way to fulfil the requirement.
- **Could have:** These are desirable but not necessary for delivery of the project and could improve the experience or satisfaction of the end product for little development cost. These will typically be included if time and resources permit.
- **Won't have (this time):** These requirements are seen by stakeholder as the least critical or not appropriate at the time. As a result, they are not planned into the schedule for delivery of the project. They are either dropped or considered for inclusion later on.

Developers will try to deliver all the *Must have*, *Should have* and *Could have* requirements, but *Should* and *Could* will be the first to be removed if the timescale does not allow for them.

⁷ Description taken from Wikipedia. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MoSCoW_Method

5. Requirements Analysis

5.1. Objective

Based on the user stories provided by the partners of the consortium and by the WP6 team itself a prioritized set of functional non-functional requirements can be gathered, which are at the core of this deliverable. They will form the starting point for the architecture development and user interface design for the unified data repository and discovery system. The input and feedback is also used to ascertain the priority of each requirement, organized according to the MoSCoW method. Basic requirements for any efficient discovery system will be expanded upon with the needs and wishes of the partners in order to meet the challenges specific to the ReIReS project, where disparate datasets are brought together to meet the needs of a wide range of researchers.

Due to the diverse nature of the consortium, the wide variety of datasets, mixed experiences and different levels of digital skill, expectations for the WP6 discovery service will be very different from partner to partner. It is also possible that certain communications on what will be included in the platform and what will not (due to time, technological or other practical constraints) will not be completely clear to all partners due to the technicality of the work package. WP6 will therefore try to actively involve as many partners as possible in the requirements analysis phase. This will help provide argumentation on why certain use cases and requirements listed by partners will not be a part of the infrastructure development plan. By working in phases, including more features with each iteration, means that some of the requested features left out in earlier stages can be added when and if time and resources allow it.

5.2. Methodology

Parallel with the use case survey, WP6 will start with creating a requirements overview document based on its own experiences with data discovery services and by researching existing digital research platforms already mentioned or used by the partners. This requirements document can be supplemented with the use cases. WP6 will then provide the requirements document to all partners for input and feedback on the gathered list of requirements and priorities given.

After a first draft made for internal review, the use cases received from partners are integrated in the requirements document and subjected to a final internal review. This document is then sent to the WP6 mailing list for review and input. The other participants in the work package besides the WP leader team offer a specialist perspective from their experience of dealing with digital sources and datasets on a daily basis.

Priorities will be indicated using the MoSCoW method, [previously outlined](#) in this deliverable. The requirements are prioritized according to both feasibility and necessity. Feasibility is judged by the technical staff working in WP6 in accordance with available time and resources. Ascertaining the necessity of a requirement is a more collaborative effort, as it is informed by the needs and wishes of the partners, as well as by a review of existing platforms.

Further details on the implementation are provided and those requirements that come from use cases will include the user story as well as a mention of the partner that provided it, as to be able to trace it to its source if further elaboration is required.

To further refine the requirements, WP6 conducted an internal review meeting to expand and to amend the actual requirements, the implementation details and the prioritization with the input of people with more technical know-how and experience. This meeting served partly as a brainstorm session with regards to requirements related to API functionalities and access management, leading to a provisional conclusion on how the accessibility of closed datasets within the ReIReS discovery platform could be approached.

5.3. Results

Because of the complexity of the project, integrating several disparate datasets for the purpose of being useful for a diverse group of researchers, it is possible that the preliminary results of the requirement analysis prove to be inadequate, incomplete or more elaborate than necessary. However, they should represent the needs of the consortium members as they are at this stage in the project. The iterative design of the unified repository allows WP6 to adjust priorities where necessary, based on this requirements overview.

The requirements overview document is set out in a simple table, as can be seen in Annex 6. The requirements are then grouped by, on the one hand, back-end requirements, which mainly relate to the delivery, processing, storage and retrieval of data, i.e. the data repository. On the other hand are the front-end requirements, such as interface, user account, reuse of data, analytics, searching and record view, i.e. the discovery system.

Most of the requirements are functional requirements, which pertain to the internal workings of the platform and describe the required behavior that needs to be implemented. After these, a much shorter list of **non-functional requirements** will be included. These try to define how well the software should work, the expected quality.⁸

The functional requirements are summarized below. The entire requirement document is too extended to be included in the text and will therefore be included as Annex 6. The requirements here are organized by category first and then by order of priority according to the MoSCoW method.

The non-functional requirements will be included in Annex 7. These will not be prioritized, however. It is too early in the project to define these requirements too specifically, as that could be a constraint on the design process.⁹

5.3.1. Back end: Data Delivery

No.	Requirement	Explanation	Priority
FR-1.1	Registration	An ingest agreement is created for each dataset	Must

⁸ Stellman, Andrew; Greene, Jennifer (2005). "Chapter 6: Software requirements". Applied Software Project Management. O'Reilly Media. pp. 97–130.

⁹ Stellman, Andrew; Greene, Jennifer (2005). "Chapter 6: Software requirements". Applied Software Project Management. O'Reilly Media. pp. 97–130.

FR-1.2	Registration	The infrastructure stores a unique code for each data provider	Must
FR-1.3	Registration	The infrastructure stores a unique code for each data set	Must
FR-1.4	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can transfer datasets of any format in a safe and efficient way	Must
FR-1.10	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can provide a response in JSON format via API	Must
FR-1.11	Update	Data provider can upload a new version of a dataset for updates	Must
FR-1.5	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can define dataset settings and upload CSV export of the dataset according to own template and perform simple mapping to ReIReS metadata elements	Should
FR-1.7	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can define dataset settings and upload XML export of the dataset	Should
FR-1.8	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can transfer XML export of the dataset via OAI-PMH	Should
FR-1.9	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can define dataset settings and upload JSON export of the dataset	Should
FR-1.6	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can upload a single digital resource and describe the object using a simple metadata template containing basic ReIReS data elements	Could

5.3.2.Back end: Data Processing

No.	Requirement	Explanation	Priority
FR-2.1	Normalization	The infrastructure supports normalization of the delivered datasets to the ReIReS data model	Must
FR-2.2	Validation	The infrastructure checks the delivered dataset against the ReIReS data model	Must
FR-2.3	Enrichment	The infrastructure supports the enrichment of the datasets with external web resources and authority databases	Should
FR-2.4	Enrichment	The infrastructure supports the mapping of controlled list/vocabularies/thesauri concepts	Should

FR-2.5	Enrichment	The infrastructure supports the extension/improvement of controlled lists/vocabularies/thesauri with new concepts and additional labels	Should
FR-2.6	Enrichment	The infrastructure supports the export of controlled lists/vocabularies/thesauri by consortium partners	Should
FR-2.7	Enrichment	The infrastructure supports machine readable full-text indexing	Could
FR-2.8	Enrichment	The infrastructure generates a thumbnail image for resources which have a link to a digital representation	Could
FR-2.9	Merging	Duplicates are merged	Won't

5.3.3. Back end: Data Storage

No.	Requirement	Explanation	Priority
FR-3.1	Permanent	Uploaded data is stored according to the ReIReS data model	Must
FR-3.2	Cache	Data accessed via API is temporarily stored in cache according to ReIReS data model for performance reasons	Must
FR-3.3	Creation/Last Update	The infrastructure stores the creation date and last update date	Must
FR-3.4	Validation	Records are validated on presence of mandatory elements	Must

5.3.4. Back end: Data Retrieval

No.	Requirement	Explanation	Priority
FR-4.2	Persistent identification	Each individual record is assigned a unique (resolvable) URI specific to ReIReS platform	Must
FR-4.1	Data output	The infrastructure provides a JSON output of the data via API according to the ReIReS data model	Should

FR-4.3	Validation	The infrastructure checks if a provided URL to a digital resource returns results	Could
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5.3.5. Back end: Reporting

No.	Requirement	Explanation	Priority
FR-5.2	Log	The log keeps track of errors	Should
FR-5.1	Ingest/Update	Data provider receives an email about the ingest/update status of the dataset	Won't

5.3.6. Front end: Interface

No.	Requirement	Explanation	Priority
FR-6.1	Language	The interface language is in English	Must
FR-6.2	Terms-of-use	A user has to accept the terms-of-use	Must
FR-6.4	Documentation	A link to a documentation/search tips page is provided	Must
FR-6.5	About	A link to an about page is provided	Must
FR-6.6	ReIReS branding	A link to the ReIReS website is provided	Must
FR-6.7	Home	A home button is provided	Must
FR-6.10	Version info	Show when the records were last updated in ReIReS	Must
FR-6.3	Feedback	A link to the feedback form for reporting issues and questions is provided	Could
FR-6.8	Font size	Change font size	Could
FR-6.9	Breadcrumb	Show/hide breadcrumb	Could

5.3.7. Front end: User account

No.	Requirement	Explanation	Priority
FR-7.1	User registration	A user can register an account	Must
FR-7.4	Account settings	Users should be able to view and edit their profiles by signing in	Must
FR-7.5	Account information	Personal information of users should be stored in accordance with GDPR	Must
FR-7.6	Access Management	User account information is provided to endpoint to be able to control access to specific datasets based on IP address	Must
FR-7.2	Sign-in/Sign-out	A user can sign-in and sign-out of his/her account	Should
FR-7.3	Delete account	A user can delete his/her account	Should
FR-7.7	Access Management	Authenticate access to specific datasets by identifying a user according to details of his account	Could
FR-7.8	Single Sign-on	User can link their account to that of their institution	Won't

5.3.8. Front end: Reuse of Data

No.	Requirement	Explanation	Priority
FR-8.4	Reference/Share	A user can copy a permalink of the record	Must
FR-8.1	Reference/Share	A citation function is available for each record	Should
FR-8.13	Favorites	A registered user can view and reuse saved queries	Should
FR-8.2	Reference/Share	A user can share a reference to a record on social media	Could
FR-8.3	Reference/Share	A user can share a reference to a search result on social media	Could

FR-8.5	Reference/Share	A user can copy a permalink for a set made on his/her profile	Could
FR-8.6	Download/Export/Print	A user can print a search result or set (basic metadata) as a PDF	Could
FR-8.7	Download/Export/Print	A user can export a search result or set (basic metadata) as JSON (ReIReS model), RIS, BibTex, Endnote, CSV file	Could
FR-8.8	Download/Export/Print	A user can download a single record as a PDF	Could
FR-8.9	Download/Export/Print	A user can export a single record as a JSON (ReIReS model), RIS, BibTex, Endnote, CSV file	Could
FR-8.10	Collect	A registered user can add records to a new or existing set on his/her profile	Could
FR-8.11	Favorites	A registered user can view and manage his/her set	Could
FR-8.12	Favorites	A registered user can add personal tags/keywords to saved records	Could
FR-8.14	Favorites	A registered user can view his/her search history on session level	Could
FR-8.15	Infrastructure	Users can use the platform to make presentations/exhibitions with the material in the database	Won't
FR-8.16	Full-text	Users are able to add comments in machine readable full text records on- and offline	Won't
FR-8.17	Distribution	ReIReS data is connected to and discoverable via Worldcat	Won't

5.3.9. Front end: Analytics

No.	Requirement	Explanation	Priority
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FR-9.1	User action logging	The infrastructure keeps track of user actions for statistics/analytics according to GDPR guidelines	Must
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5.3.10. Front end: Search

No.	Requirement	Explanation	Priority
FR-10.1	Simple search	Simple search on all metadata	Must
FR-10.2	Facets	Facets for further filtering of search results options on specific metadata	Must
FR-10.3	Browse	Browse on facet	Must
FR-10.4	Advanced search	Advanced search on any field and with AND/OR/NOT operators	Must
FR-10.7	Save query	A registered user can save queries for later reuse	Should
FR-10.10	Virtual keyboard	Virtual keyboard to easily switch to other alphabet	Should
FR-10.11	Hits	Show number of hits	Should
FR-10.5	Simple search	Include Boolean operators	Could
FR-10.6	Search	Support for search with wildcard	Could
FR-10.9	Transliteration	Platform recognizes transliteration of different scripts	Could
FR-10.12	Full-text	Search options include machine readable full text search	Could
FR-10.13	Search matching	Auto-complete for names and titles	Could
FR-10.14	Advanced search	Authority list search	Could
FR-10.15	Search matching	Fuzzy search/approximate string matching	Could
FR-10.8	Save query	E-mail alerts for new results for a saved query	Won't

5.3.11. Front end: Search Results

No.	Requirement	Explanation	Priority
FR-11.1	Overview	Basic metadata is shown in search result overview	Must
FR-11.3	Sorting	Search results can be sorted	Should
FR-11.5	Pagination	Support of pagination/load more results in case of large number of results	Should
FR-11.2	Overview	Users see why the results are relevant to their query when possible	Could
FR-11.4	Grouping	Search results can be grouped together	Could
FR-11.6	Overview	Hit-highlighting in machine readable full text search	Could

5.3.12. Front end: Record View

No.	Requirement	Explanation	Priority
FR-12.1	Record	Basic metadata is shown in search result overview	Must
FR-12.4	Reuse	License and rights information clearly published and visible in each record	Must
FR-12.10	Browsing	A link to the original record at the data provider's location is provided in each record	Must
FR-12.3	Previous/next item	A user can go to the previous/next item of his search results	Should
FR-12.2	Similar items	Similar items are shown	Could
FR-12.5	Related	Show more related metadata in database	Could
FR-12.6	Related	Show enrichments	Could
FR-12.7	Browsing	Support of machine readable full text navigation options	Could
FR-12.8	Related	Connecting primary and secondary sources	Won't

FR-12.9	Record linking	Records related to the same source/name/concept include links to one and other	Won't
FR-12.11	Browsing	A link that allows a query to be repeated in the native dataset	Won't

5.3.13. Non-Functional Requirements

Besides the functional requirements, some non-functional requirements were also described.

Back end

No.	Requirement & Subcategory	Explanation
NFR-1	Performance: Response time	The time the system takes to react to input
NFR-2	Performance: Throughput	The maximum rate of processing
NFR-3	Performance: Efficiency	Efficient resource usage for specific performance requirements
NFR-4	Scalability: Traffic	Number of organizations and users
NFR-5	Scalability: Resource allocation	Ease of resource allocation to accommodate changing load
NFR-6	Availability and Recoverability: Performance	Monitor the ability to maintain an accepted level of performance over time
NFR-7	Availability and Recoverability: Errors	Recovery from errors
NFR-8	Data Security and Integrity: GDPR compliant	Data is handled conforming to GDPR guidelines
NFR-9	Usability: Efficiency	The system functions efficiently for users
NFR-10	API: API endpoint	API access can be put on hold
NFR-11	Interoperability: Technical interoperability	Use services from and provide services to other systems

Front end

No.	Requirement & Subcategory	Explanation
NFR-12	Interface: User friendly	The interface gives a clear overview of available functions and data
NFR-13	Interface: ReIReS branding	ReIReS design principles are used for ReIReS discovery platform design
NFR-14	Interface: Language	Infrastructure must support extension to multiple interface languages
NFR-15	Interface: Design framework	Responsive design
NFR-16	Usability: Documentation	A documentation/search tips page is provided to guide new users
NFR-17	Usability: Ease to learn	The design of the interface and related documentation aim for a fast learning curve
NFR-18	Usability: Satisfying for a target user community	The platform is designed with its users in mind

5.4. Implementation

The results of this requirements analysis will be translated into the technical architecture and components of the ReIReS platform. This starts with a research and design phase selecting suitable hard- and software components and drafting a detailed development plan to achieve the requirements. This implementation is part of Task 6.3 (Architecture design & development) of WP6. Due to the iterative design of the data repository and search platform, priorities of functionalities could be subject to change or re-evaluation. The functional and non-functional requirements are the first input for the technical specification and remain essential guidelines. For the first iteration, priority will be given to fulfilling those requirements prioritized as 'Must', as they and other requirements become more clearly specified from a technical standpoint.

Annex 1. Preparation document data survey

Data survey of WP6 - Resource Discovery and Linking for Religious Studies

Introduction

WP6 has the objective to bring together the numerous digital resources and databases already available in the domain of religious studies, both from public research institutions and from commercial publishers, and make them available via a unified data repository and discovery system.

The output of WP6 will be:

- A domain specific metadata model for religious data based on international standards to improve data exchange and interpretation between systems and people;
- A unified data repository and discovery system for the domain of religious studies, based on 2 different data access mechanisms:
 - a data hub or data warehouse where metadata from different providers are imported into a central database,
 - a data exploration and discovery service or federated search where data are queried and retrieved directly from the provider by means of API instead of importing them into a central database;
- A network of interlinked concept schemes according to the Simple Knowledge Organisation System (SKOS) to allow semantic enrichment and multilingual retrieval of the datasets;
- A set of technical guidelines and metadata mapping specifications to allow new data providers to connect their data sources to the ReIReS data space, either through APIs (data discovery) or by aggregation (data hub);
- Training material for researchers involved in the testing and evaluation of the different releases of the environment.

For a full description of WP6 see proposal text.

The purpose of this survey:

In first place, WP6 will focus on providing access to a selection of datasets managed by the ReIReS consortium partners. This survey is meant to gather an overview of the datasets managed by the ReIReS partners and provide some first insight into the technical interoperability of these datasets. Based on this information we will continue the analysis process by contacting the different data specialists and technical people to discuss their datasets, used data models and technical exchange options in more detail. This work will result in:

- A selection of suitable datasets for the early demonstrator of the unified data repository and discovery system (T6.4) based on their content and technical suitability to fit one of the two cases (data hub or discovery service);

- An overview of the existing datasets within the consortium to be published as a registry of resources on the project website created by WP8.

Note:

More small surveys will be send out during the project to gather information about available data, but also about your needs concerning access to this data via the virtual research environment WP6 will develop. We prefer to work with smaller surveys on a regular basis rather than sending out one big questionnaire. By doing so we aim to reach the right people and hope that they will be able to find the time to fill out the form. We appreciate your input. It will help us with the development of a platform for Religious Studies that covers both your institution's needs and the researchers we want to reach.

This is a preparation document. For completion of the survey, you must use the online survey form. Click [here](#) to go to the form.

- Each partner must fill out at least one survey form.
- If you do not have any digital data to contribute, select no at question "Do you have digital data available that is relevant for the ReIReS project" and the survey will be finished.
- If you have more than one dataset, repeat the survey form for each dataset.

1. General Information

Name of the institution	
Name and acronym	
Primary contact for the project	
Name and surname	
Job title	
Telephone number	
Email address	

2. Data information (repeat for each dataset)

a. Identification	
Do you have digital data available that is relevant for the ReIReS project? Yes/No	If no, end of survey.
Title of the dataset	
Short description of the dataset	

Language(s) of the metadata	
Does the dataset contains (links to) media? Yes/No	
Does the media contain full text? Yes/No	
b. Data contact	Person that knows the data, works on the data, can explain more about how the data is organized (e.g. used standard, in-house metadata model, reference to images...).
Name and surname	
Job title	
Telephone number	
Email address	
c. Technical contact	Person that knows more about the technical interoperability of the data (e.g. export formats, harvesting protocols, API specification...).
	Please complete when different from data contact.
Name and surname	
Job title	
Telephone number	
Email address	
d. Access information	Is the data accessible on the Web? Is it freely accessible or do users need to subscribe? Are there costs attached to the subscription?
	We understand that not all data can be publicly available. User authentication and registration protocols data discovery platform will therefore be including open, partially open and restricted access policies to datasets.

<p>Online: Yes, free access</p> <p>Yes, free after registration</p> <p>Yes, paid access</p> <p>No, not accessible on the web</p> <p>Other</p>	
If no or other, please provide more information	
URL to online dataset	
<p>Are you willing to publish data on the data repository & discovery platform to be developed?</p> <p>Yes/No/No, because the resource is not owned by our institution/organisation</p>	
If no, please tell why and if you are willing to provide access under certain conditions?	
Other comments about access.	
Please provide account details if registration is needed for review of the dataset. This account information will not be distributed.	
e. Technical details	
<p>Use of standards (incl. domain ontologies)</p>	<p>A standard is an agreed, repeatable way of doing something. It is a published document that contains a technical specification or other precise criteria designed to be used consistently as a rule, guideline, or definition.</p> <p>Some common standards are MARC, ISAD(G), TEI, MIDAS-heritage ...</p>
<p>Is your data organised according to a standard?</p> <p>Yes/No</p>	

<p>If yes, what standard:</p> <p>Name</p> <p>URL standard specification documentation</p>	
<p>Did you make changes/extensions to the standard? Yes, No</p>	
<p>If yes, are these changes/extensions documented? Yes/No</p>	
<p>If you are using an in-house data model, is this model documented and used consistently? Yes, no</p>	
<p>Please provide more information about your data model, especially if you are using an in-house model or adapted a standard to your needs.</p>	
<p>Upload data documentation if available</p>	
<p>Other comments about standards and used data models</p>	
<p>Use of controlled vocabularies/thesauri/terminologies</p>	
<p>Are you using controlled vocabularies for the metadata description? Yes/No</p>	
<p>If yes, please list them with name, data element for which they are used (e.g. subject classification) and language(s).</p>	
<p>Other comments about controlled vocabularies</p>	
<p>Data interoperability - machine-readable format</p>	E.g. XML, JSON, CSV
<p>Is your data exportable in a machine-readable format? Yes/No</p>	
<p>If yes, in what format(s)?</p>	

Data interoperability - harvesting schema	E.g. XSD EAD, LIDO XSD, MARC XML schema, Schema.org, ...
Is your data export structured according to a standard harvesting schema? Yes/No	
If yes, in what schema(s)? Name URL harvesting schema specification	
Data interoperability - harvesting protocols	E.g. OAI-PMH
Do you support harvesting protocols? Yes/No	
If yes, what protocol(s)? Name	
Data interoperability - API access	
Do you provide API access to your data? Yes/No	
If yes, Is API documentation available: Yes/No URL API documentation if available online	
f. Dependencies	
Does the data contain systematical links to other [external/internal] systems or data sets? Yes/No	
If yes, please explain	
Is the data set used as a target destination for other systems or data sets? Yes/No	
If yes, please explain	
Is the data application (e.g. database, website, software) managed in-house or by an external partner? In-house	

External partner	
If external partner provide Name Explanation	
g. Updates	
Is the data set final/static or will the database be updated on a regular basis? Final/Updated	
If updated, please explain.	E.g. frequency of updates...
h. Other information	
Other relevant information related to the dataset	

3. Additional remarks/questions

Annex 2. ReIReS WP6 Data Survey Form

ReIReS WP6 Data Survey

This survey is meant to gather an overview of the datasets managed by the ReIReS partners and provide some first insight into the technical interoperability of these datasets.

Name of the institution *

<input type="text" value="Example"/>	<input type="text" value="Ex"/>
--------------------------------------	---------------------------------

Name
Acronym
Name and acronym as mentioned in the Grant Agreement.

Primary contact for the project *

<input type="text" value="Example"/>	<input type="text" value="Example"/>
--------------------------------------	--------------------------------------

First
Last

Job title

Phone

Please add your country calling code. E.g. 003216379419

Email *

Do you have digital data available that is relevant for the ReIReS project? *

yes
 no

Data information

You have to submit one survey form for each dataset!

Title of the dataset *

Short description of the dataset *

Language(s) of the metadata *

Does the dataset contains (links to) media? *

yes
 no

ReIReS WP6 Data Survey

This survey is meant to gather an overview of the datasets managed by the ReIReS partners and provide some first insight into the technical interoperability of these datasets.

Does the media contain full text? *

yes

no

Data contact

Person that knows the data, works on the data, can explain more about how the data is organized (e.g. used standard, in-house metadata model, reference to images...).

Name

First

Last

Job title

Phone

Please add your country calling code. E.g. 003216379419

Email

Technical contact

Person that knows more about the technical interoperability of the data (e.g. export formats, harvesting protocols, API specification...). Please complete when different from data contact!

Name

First

Last

Please complete when different from data contact!

Job title

Please complete when different from data contact!

Phone

Please complete when different from data contact! Please add your country calling code. E.g. 003216379419

Email

Please complete when different from data contact!

ReIReS WP6 Data Survey

This survey is meant to gather an overview of the datasets managed by the ReIReS partners and provide some first insight into the technical interoperability of these datasets.

Is the data accessible on the Web? Is it freely accessible or do users need to subscribe? Are there costs attached to the subscription? *

- Yes, free access
- Yes, free after registration
- Yes, paid access
- No, not accessible on the web
- Other

We understand that not all data can be publicly available. User authentication and registration protocols data discovery platform will therefore be including open, partially open and restricted access policies to datasets.

URL of online dataset *

Are you willing to publish data on the data repository & discovery platform to be developed by WP6? *

- yes
- no
- no, because the resource is not owned by our institution/organisation

Other comments about access.

Use of standards (incl. domain ontologies)

A standard is an agreed, repeatable way of doing something. It is a published document that contains a technical specification or other precise criteria designed to be used consistently as a rule, guideline, or definition. E.g. MARC, TEI...

Is your data organised according to a standard? *

- yes
- no

Name of standard *

E.g. MARC, ISAD(G), TEI, MIDAS-heritage ...

URL of standard specification documentation *

E.g. https://www.loc.gov/marc/bibliographic/

Did you make changes/extensions to the standard? *

- yes
- no

ReIReS WP6 Data Survey

This survey is meant to gather an overview of the datasets managed by the ReIReS partners and provide some first insight into the technical interoperability of these datasets.

Upload data documentation if available.

 Drag & Drop (or) [Choose File](#)

Other comments about standards and used data models.

Use of controlled vocabularies/thesauri/terminologies

Are you using controlled vocabularies for the metadata description? *

- yes
 no

Other comments about controlled vocabularies

Data interoperability - machine-readable format

E.g. XML, JSON, CSV

Is your data exportable in a machine-readable format? *

- yes
 no

If yes, in what format(s)? *

XML, JSON, CSV

Data interoperability - harvesting schema

E.g. OAI-PMH

Do you support harvesting protocols? *

- yes
 no

ReIReS WP6 Data Survey

This survey is meant to gather an overview of the datasets managed by the ReIReS partners and provide some first insight into the technical interoperability of these datasets.

If yes, what protocol(s)? *

OAI-PMH

Please provide the name(s) of the protocol(s) and any other relevant information such as a web reference.

Data interoperability – API access

Do you provide API access to your data? *

yes

no

Is API documentation available? *

yes

no

URL to API documentation

File upload for API documentation

 Drag & Drop (or [Choose File](#))

Does the data contain systematical links to other [external/internal] systems or data sets? *

yes

no

E.g. references to other databases or online resources such as VIAF.

Is the data set used as a target destination for other systems or data sets? *

yes

no

Is the data application (e.g. database, website, software) managed in-house or by an external partner? *

In-house

External partner

Is the data set final/static or will the database be updated on a regular basis? *

Final

Updated

ReIReS WP6 Data Survey

This survey is meant to gather an overview of the datasets managed by the ReIReS partners and provide some first insight into the technical interoperability of these datasets.

Other relevant information related to the dataset.

Additional remarks/questions.

|

Annex 3. Motivation Datasets

WP6: Datasets selection for the pilot project of the ReIReS unified data repository and discovery system

In wanting to achieve interoperability and linking between dispersed digital resources and datasets related to religious and historical studies, WP6 acknowledges two different approaches.

- 1) **Aggregated search model:** Metadata from different providers is imported into a central database after mapping and normalization. User are provided with an integrated and consistent view of the metadata, but the metadata is also duplicated. New data added to the datasets of ReIReS partners that needs to be integrated into the platform would have to be imported every time.
- 2) **Federated search model:** A data exploration and discovery service allows users to query the metadata of different repositories without the need to import the records into the central database. This has the advantage of flexibility and deduplication of effort and resources, but also implies the data provider's infrastructure have the necessary API's in place for providing live access. Updates to a dataset would not require any new imports or changes to the unified platform.

The federated search model seems more efficient, but not all datasets are accessible via API. Unless both models are integrated, datasets that depend on older or less open technologies would be locked out.

A combination of these two search models means that implementation becomes much more complex. A pilot project will be necessary, to analyze the possibilities and restrictions faced in building this platform. A few datasets will have to be selected before there can be a finished project that integrates all the relevant datasets managed by the partners in the consortium. Keeping in mind the differences between these datasets, the first phase of this pilot should prioritize at least two disparate datasets, so that both aforementioned search models can be tested. The feasibility of a second and third phase depend on the time and resources available after the prioritized datasets have been integrated in the pilot project.

Phase 1

The collection of digitized manuscripts in the *Jewish Library* managed by *Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz* is a good candidate to be imported into the data repository, after mapping and normalization. It contains 36 resources and the dataset is final, which makes it easier to manage. The records are described with detailed metadata and a link to a digital representation online, a functionality that would also need to be implemented in the pilot at some point. The resources can be delivered in an XML export or could be harvested via the OAI-PMH protocol. Both methods of delivery would still require the metadata to be mapped to a shared data model. The resources in this dataset are described according to the METS/MODS standard following a DFG application profile (German Research Foundation guidelines), which means their data model is documented and therefore more efficiently and thoroughly convertible to a different standard. Prioritizing this dataset seems ideal as a first step towards formulating an integrated metadata model to be used by data providers who contribute to the ReIReS unified data repository.

Another challenge in integrating these disparate datasets is their different types of access. Whereas most are freely accessible, others offer only paid access. **Brepols Publishers**, for example does not offer free access, which means that if we want to include the data this partner has to offer, we need to prioritize one of their datasets early on, to deal with that challenge. Even though the **Index Religiosus** bibliography does not currently provide access to its metadata via API, Brepols has expressed an interest in developing and implementing this. This would make it an ideal test case for the federated search model, which would also allow for testing different access types early on in the pilot.

The digital titles of the **Maurits Sabbe Library** should perhaps also be prioritized in this first phase, seeing as how this dataset can be implemented into the ReIReS unified data repository using either method. The dataset can be exported in XML format, its records can be harvested via the OAI-PMH protocol and it is API accessible. As the library is part of **KU Leuven**, LIBIS is already well acquainted with the technology and metadata standards used for this collection, making it efficient to work with. The data is organized according to the MARC standard and the changes made to the standard have been documented. This means it is interoperable with the dataset of JGU Mainz, but considering the differences in application profiles still require analysis of metadata and ontologies.

Phase 2

In a second phase, other interesting datasets can be prioritized, preferably those whose implementation would follow the same path as that of phase one. The database of the **Annales de l'Ecole Pratique des Hautes Etudes** already offers access via API, for example. Integrating this collection would allow us to test the viability of the workflow used with the Index Religiosus on a dataset that is freely accessible. All of these records contain links to full text PDF files, whose content is also searchable.

BrepolsOnline is the platform for all online content published by Brepols in books and journals and it has standardized API's. This means federated search on the metadata is possible. The dataset itself is structured differently because of the inclusion of eBooks and online access to academic journals.

Sofia University has the dataset **Cyrrillomethodiana** for which they can provide an XML or CSV export, which could be imported into the unified data repository after mapping it to the data model used for the collection of JGU Mainz, allowing us to see the viability of that model and improving it where necessary.

Mansi Digitale, a web resource managed by **Fscire**, is only available via a CSV export that can be used to create links to the digital images from the collection. This would be a good test of the functionalities related to digital media resources in the unified ReIReS platform. The dataset itself is organized according to a consistently used in-house standard, which would require a unique mapping to a shared data model.

Phase 3

A third phase could then focus on other interesting datasets offered by the consortium members. This would provide an analysis of the flexibility and efficiency of the pilot project for the ReIReS unified data repository and discovery system.

During the progression of these phases, priorities might change and the integration of some datasets could be handled in a different phase. Although the pilot will initially include only two or three datasets, it could be possible to integrate more datasets further along in the process during later phases. At the moment, the datasets that have been prioritized, focus mainly on bibliographical data, but for the purposes of a pilot

project this is certainly warranted. Eventually it should also be possible to add authority records on people, places, etc. in the data repository, such as *Europa Sacra* and the *Dictionnaire d'histoire et de géographie ecclésiastiques* offered by Brepols or the *Clerics database* managed by JGU Mainz, to give some examples.

Annex 4. User Story Manual

User story manual

1 What are user stories

User stories represent requirements told from the perspective of the users. User stories show the added value and needs of the users.

2 How to formulate user stories

User stories should be described in short simple sentences. Preferably as follows:

As <a type of user> (WHO)

I want <to do something> (WHAT)

So that <it has a use for me> (WHY)

It is important to write your user stories while taking into consideration different types of users. Depending on the type of user (WHO), the WHAT segment may contain a completely different action due to the underlying purpose/reason (WHY).

3 Examples

- *As a registered user, I want to be able to reset my password, so I can still access the platform if I lose my password.*
- *As an archivist, I want to restrict access to the records, so I do not violate privacy laws.*
- *As a researcher, I want to save my queries, so I do not have to look for the same record every time I want to consult it.*
- *As a student, I want to browse search a specific collection, so I can see what type of collection a library has.*

4 Level of detail

In creating user stories, the focus should be on a specific main goal. This goal may be to:

- Simplify the reuse of our images.
- Accelerate the import of new records in the catalogue system.
- Display my collections online.

The aforementioned are actually also user stories, but of a more general nature (*epic stories*). Therefore, you could also formulate them as follows:

- As a research institution, I want to allow for the reuse of our images, so that the work of researchers, being the collection of study objects, becomes easier.
- As a special collection library, I want to accelerate the import of new records in the catalogue system, so that I can free up staff for other responsibilities.
- As a publisher, I want to publish our collections online, so that the so that our publications and work attract more attention.

These themes are then split up further into more specific user stories according to specific types of users and purposes.

- As a university library, I want to make images (that are free of access rights) available for download by third parties, so that they do not need to return to our website every time they need it.
- As an end-user, I want to download a specific image, so that I can consult it offline.
- As a researcher, I want to download all the images of a manuscript, so that I can preserve it in my digital archive.

It is not necessary to give technical solutions or to mention specific products in these user stories, or to describe the desired solution in detail (i.e. all images need to be made available in JPEG format). This limits the investigation of different types of (technical) solutions.

5 Methods

The aforementioned examples only show short descriptions of the user stories. They are reminders of the needs/requirements of the partner. It is not the intention of user stories to describe the functionality entirely or in detail. It is much more effective to exchange detailed information in a conversation.

After a short internal discussion (LIBIS), to formulate further questions, the user stories are reviewed with the partners to further clarify the desired effects of the user stories, to exchange ideas, and to specify potential first priorities.

Afterwards the user stories are converted into requirements (LIBIS and partners). Thereafter LIBIS does a preliminary investigation into the technical feasibility and potential solutions, including a calculation of the necessary resources (hard- and software + staff).

The requirements analysis and calculation of costs are finalized in further consultation with the partner. After that priorities are indicated, together with the partner, for which the MoSCoW-method¹⁰ can be used.

6 Template

See 'User story template.xlsx'.

¹⁰ M - must have: these requirements have to be present in the final result, without them the final product is unusable;

S - should have: these requirements are very desirable, but without them the product can be used;

C - could have: these requirements will only be implemented if there is enough time;

W - won't have: these requirements will not be featured in this project, but could be interesting for a follow up project in the future.

Annex 5. Use Case Template

ID	MAIN PURPOSE	THEME	AS	I WANT	SO THAT	Notes	Provided by
1	Finding records	User friendly	a researcher	the option to save queries	I can regularly check for new records related to my research		LIBIS
2	Disclosing records	Download	a researcher	to download a fully digitized manuscript	I can consult it offline		LIBIS
3	Reuse of images	Non-functional	publisher	clearly visible license agreements	the users know how they can use the image	i.e. show license and user agreement before download	LIBIS
4	User-friendliness	Profile	a researcher	to own an account	I can customize my preferences		LIBIS
5		Database	collection expert	access to the data repository	I can update the platform when a new item is added to my collection	i.e. there needs to be a solution to keep the ReIReS platform up to date with the partner collections	LIBIS
6	Using records	Citations	a researcher	a tool to export citations of records	I can efficiently add records to my research bibliography		LIBIS
7	User-friendliness	Searching	a researcher	auto-complete while searching records	queries are suggested when I am unsure about spelling		LIBIS
8	Overview	Browsing	a researcher	to sort query results	I can arrange them according to oldest or newest		LIBIS
9	Providing context		an institution	my collection on the unified platform to be identifiable as mine	users can discover what my institution has to offer		LIBIS
10	Searching persons	Searching	a researcher	the possibility to search persons linked to different international/national normed data / thesauri	I can search for a certain person in all databases	i.e.: entity: person with different relations using inter-/national normed data / thesauri e.g. German GND, VIAF and using linked data	JGU Mainz
11	Searching places	Searching	a researcher	the possibility to search places linked to different international/national normed geo-data / geo- thesauri	I can search for a certain place in all databases	i.e. entity: place with different relations using inter-/national normed data / thesauri e.g. German GND, Geonames and using linked data, e.g. commons.pelagios.org	JGU Mainz
12	cataloguing	Download / Upload	librarian / collection expert	the option to down- or upload meta-data / catalogue records of manuscripts, digitized manuscripts and othe media	I can reuse datarecords	i.e. using international cataloguing or metadata formats, e.g. marc, mets, mods, dublin core e.g. using xml, rdf or other metainteroperable formats	JGU Mainz
13	Searching Subject Headings	Searching	a researcher	the possibility to search subject headings linked to different international / national normed data / thesauri	I can search for a certain subject heading in all databases	i.e. entity: subject heading with different relations using inter-/national normed data / thesauri e.g. German GND, and using linked data	JGU Mainz
14	Datamining	Datamining	a researcher	the option to use automatical datamining tools to look for different data	I can use datamining tools to look through large amounts of data automatically	API Interoperability OAI-PMH	JGU Mainz

15	platform	infrastructure	an institution	the option to provide a platform with workflows, databases, technical possibilities presenting as well insitutions as their content, databases ...	I can reuse infrastructure, workflows of similar projects, e.g. for several regions, but the same topic	e.g. Bavarikon as platform eg. Bavarikon-Merkblatt für Virtuelle Ausstellungen for a workflow	JGU Mainz
16	categorizing	infrastructure	all	the opinion to categorize the data	I can differ between e.g. databases, collections of pictures or 3D-Objects or all objects, texts, maps, bibliographies		JGU Mainz
18	interdisciplina ry	relations	all	the possibility to link to subjects related to religion	I can link e.g. to art / iconography / saints	allowance to link also to related subjects although it is a religious database	JGU Mainz
19			a university library	to include the specific collections in WorldCat	they would be found by searchers, who not specifically looking for them	if its possible make the ReIRes collections as a seperate collection also accessible by Worldcat	Apeldoorn
20			a university library / a researcher	to search in WorldCat and to have directly access to the found records	I do not have to search through another search engine again		Apeldoorn
21							Apeldoorn
22			a researcher	to have clear search filters	I find specific results	i.e. boolean operators, truncation, combinations multiple search terms	Apeldoorn
23							Apeldoorn
24			a researcher	to make a search and history builder and save this	I do not missing results		Apeldoorn
25							Apeldoorn
26			a researcher	to be able to print or download or send by mail results and full texts	I consult these offline		Apeldoorn
27	Dissemination	User friendly	all user	to access and download metadata	I can steer my research		CNR
28			a registered user	to change password and my profile	I can always access to platform and describe my competencies and skills		CNR
29	Finding records		a student	to browse search a specific collection	I can see what type of collection is	i.e. show titles and metadata of any level of collections. Show a description of the collection	CNR
30	Insert records	Archive standard	an Institution (University, Research centre, Archive or Library)	to insert entire collection and describe it with current standard of depository	The collection will be achieved and archived in a universal way		CNR
31	Insert records	Archive standard	an Institution (University, Research centre, Archive or Library)	to easy insert new documents in an existing collection	I can reuse immediatley the new material insert into its own described collection		CNR

32	Reuse of images		an Institution (University, Research centre, Archive or Library)	to download a fully digitized manuscript or collection and let it available for Institution's users and partners	Users and partners can not return on the Institute website. In this way we guarantee a full access of disclosing records into Institutions		CNR
33	Finding records	User friendly	all user	to do a thematic research by subject	I can steer my research	i.e. I can research by name, surname, archive, fund, city, country, religious order, ...	CNR
34	Finding words / looking for texts	searching	a researcher	to find particular texts I am already aware of (e.g. biblical quotations or technical words)	I know where I may find sources that are common for a diverse set of conciliar texts		FSCIRE
35	finding texts	searching	a researcher	to know whether there are texts that may occur several times (by direct or indirect quotation) in a set of sources	on the basis of the status of the art, I can quickly discover common sources that are not already known to the scholarship		FSCIRE
36	locating sources	searching	a researcher	to locate on a page (pdf) the exact beginning/end of an indirect quotation	we can immediately recognize the border between source and commentary/use of the source	this is a particular case of ID #2	FSCIRE
37	User-friendliness	browsing	a researcher	to insert in a off-line mode my commentaries to texts which are on line	when I read on-line texts my computer displays and merge the my comments and the source I am studying		FSCIRE
38	Constructing a Hyperlinks network	Database	a collection expert / a researcher	to connect several documents of my database	when I come across a particular source/name/concept which occurs elsewhere in the corpus of texts I have uploaded, I can have an immediate 'map' of all the occurrences		FSCIRE
39	Constructing a Hyperlinks network	Database	a collection expert / a researcher	to connect words/concepts of the texts of my database with bibliography records of a library catalogue	we have a tool to connect primary and secondary sources (i.e. ancient texts and scholarship which has been produced on their themes		FSCIRE
40	Usage reporting		publisher/institution	collect statistics on (dataset/platform) usage	I can provide feedback to institutions on platform/dataset usage.	https://www.projectcounter.org/	Brepols
41	access management		publisher	manage access to a dataset	I can control who accesses a dataset	- for deposit - for api	Brepols
42	Navigating results	Browsing	end user	click through to the native dataset-record	I can see the full record in its native context		Brepols
43	Navigating results	Browsing	end user	click trough to repeat the search in the native-dataset	I can see the full result list within a specific dataset, and drill up/down	- e.g. walk found manuscript results in the native database. Or further drill down the search in the target database	Brepols
44	data management		dataset admin	update data for an existing (deposited) dataset	I can provide improved / updated data		Brepols
45	platform management		platform admin	remove a dataset (not just the data, but the full participation)	I can pull back access to content in case of conflict, error, ...	both for api / deposit	Brepols

46	platform management		platform admin	set up a new a dataset (not just the data, but the participation of a dataset)	To support a new participant / database	both for api / deposit	Brepols
47	data management		dataset admin	remove a data for a deposited dataset	To ensure data is no longer available on the platform.		Brepols
48	Finding records	User friendly	end user	dataset/facet drill-down			Brepols
49	platform management		dataset admin	put an API access on hold	I can perform maintenance / downtime on the endpoint		Brepols
50	platform management		platform admin	assess result scoring of the datasets	I can benchmark/monitor search result scoring over the datasets	This can guarantee or help improve scoring over datasets	Brepols
51	access management		endpoint	receive user-identification data (api-key/ip/pwd/...)	authenticate and authorize	For API to authorize user(type)	Brepols
52	access management		publisher	determine visibility of information per user profile	I can server different data views to different user types.	Maybe API can self handle this, but deposit may not. There may be different access rights within the same dataset!	Brepols
53	data management		consortium	manage central onthology	It can be improved / extended	Not sure who can do this, by what agreement	Brepols
54	data management		consortium	manage translations	I can better map on datasets in another language	Not sure who can do this, by what agreement	Brepols
55	data management		dataset admin	export central onthology	I can map internal thesauri / keywords on it		Brepols
56	data management		dataset admin	validate a (new) set of data	I am sure it matches the requirements		Brepols
57	Unified search engine (federated search)	searching	a researcher	To search in ReiRes Database threw library engines.	I can find the resources threw the library search engine		EPHE
58	Vizualize the libraries	searching	a researcher	See the location of a physical resource (book, manuscrit) on a map.	I can find easily the libraries in order to acces to the original document		EPHE
59	Searching by date when the resource was added	searching	a researcher	To find recently added resources.	I can be informed about the new resources		EPHE
60	Sorting by type	sorting	a researcher	To find and sort resources by type.	I can find and compare similar resources.		EPHE
61	Sorting by source	sorting	a researcher	To find and sort resources by data source.	I can find the resources provided by an institution.		EPHE
62	Advanced search	searching	a researcher	To search only in a specific dataset.	I avoid having search results that do not corresponds to what I'm looking for.		EPHE

63	Citing the resource	citations	a researcher	To obtain a persistent identifier of a resource.	I can quote the resource in a paper or online publication.		EPHE
64	Use statistics	infrastructure	an institution	To obtain anonymous statistics and analytics (number of users, search keywords) of the resources that I provide to ReIReS.	The research institution or laboratory can produce easily the reports about the use of data that they provide to ReIReS.		EPHE
65	Export data references	export/download	a researcher	To export a data (or search results) in a reference management software (Zotero, EndNote, etc.)	I can manage the references for my own research.		EPHE
66	Find resources	searching	a researcher	To select keywords and receive a notification when a new data related to the selected keywords is added.	I can be informed about the new data about my field of research.		EPHE
67	Centralize authentication	sign in	a researcher	To use an institutional single sign-on (Shibboleth) in order to access to my account in ReIReS platform.	I do not need to create a new ReIReS account, I can use my institutional authentication.		EPHE
68			a researcher and programmer	to access databases via an API	I can automatize the download of datasets and/or join the data with my own local databases	e.g. to realize queries that are too complex for the build-in search mechanisms OR to visualize the data in more sophisticated ways (network graphs, maps etc.) OR to build import modules for citation managers or homemade databases etc.	JGU Mainz
69			a researcher	to use query languages	I can realize more complex queries than the usual search for author/title/location/time in combination with wildcards etc.	what about SPARQL?	JGU Mainz
70			a researcher	to benefit from linked data	I can evaluate connections between datasets that go beyond the usual datamodels (author/title/location/time/tags)	e.g. book B is a new edition of book A; this journal article is cited by X, Y and Z; show me the books of author M that were printed in France OR Latin America (connect the database to wikidata etc. to get country/continent); show me all books that were printed when the author was already dead (connect the database to wikidata etc. to get the author's date of death)	JGU Mainz

71			a researcher	to have persistant URIs/URLs for digitized sources AND I want to look them up in ONE place	I don't have to mess around with things like http://books.google.com/books?id=123abcAAABBBCCC and the whole zoo of different IDs etc.	I search the database, I find my resource (with its persistant URL) and get a list of all the URLs where I can find digitized copies (Google Books, Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, Early English Books etc.). If I could access the database via API I could even build direct links to the digitized copies without collecting all the different URLs myself. One persistant URL would be sufficient.	JGU Mainz
72			a researcher	to see as much IDs/shelf marks/URLs as possible in one place	I don't have to switch to local catalogues to check in which libraries/databases the resource is available	A few databases already offer this service on a national level, e.g. https://zdb-katalog.de or https://kvk.bibliothek.kit.edu	JGU Mainz
73			a researcher	to browse tag structures (e.g. the local tags/subject headings or standardized tagging systems like the "Regensburger Verbundklassifikation" https://rvk.uni-regensburg.de/)	I can understand better how the items were tagged by the librarians (structure of tags, etc.) AND develop better search strategies	In many catalogues / databases the structure of the tags / notation / subject headings is not accessible to normal users; visualization of this structure would be very helpful (e.g. as a tree, mind map, network graph etc.)	JGU Mainz
74			a researcher	to take a look at the network formed by persons, texts, printing locations and publishing dates	I can get a visual impression of the connections between these data points that are normally presented as a mere table	Some catalogues have already implemented elements like that: e.g. publication timeline: http://www.worldcat.org/identities/lccn-nr93019099/ , mapping of printing locations: https://viaf.org/viaf/67289615/ Nevertheless I think these implementations are not flexible enough: One should be able to combine complex queries with powerful visualization tools!	JGU Mainz

N°	Where	Requirement	Subcategory	Requirement	Implementation details	Dependencies	Priority	Use case	Provided by	More information
BACK-END										
FR-1 Data Delivery										
FR-1.1	NA	Data delivery	Registration	An ingest agreement is created for each dataset	The ingest agreement stands outside of the ReIReS-DP. It is a document that includes important information for the integration of the dataset into the system. It will include information such as rights, license, access status of the specific data set, type info (e.g. book, manuscript, database, full text, archival document...), as well as administrative information such as contact details, data provider code, data set code, language(s) of the dataset etc. This document will also contain an agreement on the upload procedure, e.g. if the mapping/normalization of the dataset is taken care of by WP6.		Must	"As platform admin I want to set up a new dataset (not just the data, but the participation of a dataset) so to support a new participant / database" "As a publisher I want to manage access to a dataset so that I can control who accesses a dataset"	WP6 contributors	Use case Brepols
FR-1.2	Back-end	Data delivery	Registration	The infrastructure stores a unique code for each data provider	This is a consistent identifier for the source of the dataset		Must		WP6 Leader	Remark: The unique code will help data providers to easily find (and export) their data in the ReIReS-DP, since a name is not guaranteed to be unique.
FR-1.3	Back-end	Data delivery	Registration	The infrastructure stores a unique code for each data set	This could have the following structure: dataprovider_dataset		Must		WP6 Leader	easily find (and export) a specific dataset in the ReIReS-DP, since a name is not guaranteed to be unique. Also this code, together with the data provider code, should be used in the communication when new versions are delivered of
FR-1.4	Back-end	Data delivery	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can transfer datasets of any format (XML, JSON, CSV, Spreadsheet such as Excel) in a safe and efficient way	This could be an FTP transfer mechanism. Should support transfer of big files. This is an early transfer mechanism. In later stages of the project more elaborate upload and transfer mechanisms will be implemented depending on available time, resources and priority (R1.5 - R1.9).		Must		WP6 Leader	Remark: Simple transfer mechanisms can be used in the early stages of the project. In later stages or next project more refined upload mechanisms where data providers can define their dataset and possibly map to basic ReIReS data elements should/could be included.
FR-1.5	Back-end	Data delivery	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can define dataset settings and upload CSV export of the dataset according to own template and perform simple mapping to ReIReS metadata elements	Step 1: Select data provider from drop-down list, enter dataset code provided as part of the ingest agreement, browse folder - upload CSV. Step 2: define CSV separators. Step 3: Map columns to ReIReS basic metadata elements. This is only meant for basic mapping and upload. It is not intended to support the full ReIReS metadata model.		Should	"As an Institution (University, Research center, Archive or Library) I want to insert entire collection and describe it with current standard of depository so that The collection will be achieved and archived in a universal way"	WP6 contributors	Use case CNR
FR-1.6	Back-end	Data delivery	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can upload a single digital resource and describe the object using a simple metadata template containing basic ReIReS data elements	Step 1: Select data provider code from drop-down list, enter basic metadata for the single object including rights, license and access status info. In case of online resource, add link to resource in metadata. If no version is available online, upload file. Step 2: Submit data upload. This is only meant for basic upload of single resource metadata descriptions for discovery purposes in case there is no metadata record existing or if resource is not available online. Upload limited to 50 GB. Total upload limited for data providing partner.		Could	"As an Institution (University, Research center, Archive or Library) I want to easy insert new documents in an existing collection so that I can reuse immediately the new material insert into its own described collection"	WP6 contributors	Use case CNR
FR-1.7	Back-end	Data delivery	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can define dataset settings and upload XML export of the dataset	Step 1: Select data provider from drop-down list, enter dataset code provided as part of the ingest agreement, browse folder - upload of XML. In case of XML, normalization to ReIReS data model is always done by WP6 (only if part of the ingest agreement).		Should		WP6 Leader	
FR-1.8	Back-end	Data delivery	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can transfer XML export of the dataset via OAI-PMH	OAI-PMH deposit should contain data provider code and dataset code (ListSets). In case of XML, normalization to ReIReS data model is always done by WP6 (only if part of the ingest agreement).		Should		WP6 Leader	
FR-1.9	Back-end	Data delivery	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can define dataset settings and upload JSON export of the dataset	Step 1: Select data provider from drop-down list, enter dataset code provided as part of the ingest agreement, browse folder - upload of JSON. Normalization to ReIReS data model is done by WP6 (only if part of ingest agreement) or delivered according to the JSON ReIReS model.		Should		WP6 Leader	
FR-1.10	Back-end	Data delivery	Upload/Transfer	Data provider can provide a response in JSON format via API	Normalization to ReIReS data model is done by WP6 (only if agreed in the ingest agreement) or can be delivered according to the JSON ReIReS model.		Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-1.11	Back-end	Data delivery	Update	Data provider can upload a new version of a dataset for updates	Data provider should include data provider code and data set code. Each uploaded record should contain a identifier on the basis of which the update can take place.	R1.2, R1.3	Must	"As dataset admin I want to update data for an existing (deposited) dataset so that I can provide improved / updated data"	WP6 contributors	Use case Brepols

R2 Data Processing

FR-2.1	Back-end	Data processing	Normalization	The infrastructure supports normalization of the delivered datasets to the ReIReS data model	Normalization to ReIReS data model is done by WP6 if agreed in the ingest agreement. The project partners will not be using the data mapping and normalization tools. They either deliver the data according to the agreed JSON format or it is agreed during the preparation of the ingest agreement that WP6 will take up normalization for them.		Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-2.2	Back-end	Data processing	Validation	The infrastructure checks the delivered dataset against the ReIReS data model	In case data is delivered immediately in the ReIReS data model (JSON delivery via API), the JSON is checked and validated against the ReIReS data model. In case a dataset is delivered through another method (XML upload, XML OAI-PMH transfer) and normalized by WP6, the data is reviewed on presence of mandatory metadata elements.		Must	"As dataset admin I want to validate a (new) set of data so that I am sure it matches the requirements"	WP6 contributors	Use case Brepols
FR-2.3	Back-end	Data processing	Enrichment	The infrastructure supports the enrichment of the datasets with external web resources and authority databases	Make a clear distinction between provided and automatically created (enriched) metadata. E.g. linking of person names to VIAF, subject to Library of Congress subject headings, GeoNames for place name information ...		Should		WP6 Leader	
FR-2.4	Back-end	Data processing	Enrichment	The infrastructure supports the mapping of controlled list/vocabularies/thesauri concepts	Based on authority lists. E.g. adding multiple language labels for concepts used by the ReIReS consortium		Should	"As consortium I want to manage translations so that I can better map on datasets in another language"	WP6 contributors	Use case Brepols

R4 Data Retrieval										
FR-4.1	Back-end	Retrieval	Data output	The infrastructure provides a JSON output of the data via API according to the ReIReS data model	The API JSON output can be used to service the front-end. Front-end service will have full access. Partners (and 3rd party services if approved by the consortium) can receive an API key for access to the openly accessible datasets only. Access status for 3th parties via API can be set as part of the metadata (0 = not accessible via API, 1 = accessible via API). Status to be defined in the ingest agreement.		Should	"As a researcher I want the option to use automatically datamining tools to look for different data so that I can use datamining tools to look through large amounts of data automatically" "As librarian / collection expert I want the option to down- or upload meta-data / catalogue records of manuscripts, digitized manuscripts and other media so that I can reuse data records"	WP6 contributors	Use case JGU. Remark: Dataset will only be provided in JSON format. Supporting additional formats would require too much work and is out of scope. There are however multiple tools available for transforming JSON to other formats (e.g. JSON to CSV).
FR-4.2	Back-end	Retrieval	Persistent identification	Each individual record is assigned a unique (resolvable) URI specific to ReIReS platform	This allows for uniform identification of the record and persistent and consistent access to it via web browser if resolvable		Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-4.3	Back-end	Retrieval	Validation	The infrastructure checks if a provided URL to a digital resource returns results	Manual: e.g. yearly check to see if URL is still resolvable OR Automated: In case a URL is included in the metadata record for reference to a digital resource, the system checks if the URL still returns a result. In case of an error (e.g. Error 404), the record is not displayed in the results list and logged for reporting to the partner.		Could		WP6 Leader	
R5 Reporting										
FR-5.1	Back-end	Reporting	Ingest/Update	Data provider receives an email about the ingest/update status of the dataset	Automatic mailing of ingest/update status		Won't		WP6 Leader	Remark: Manual procedure during the project. Later on, when more data providers join, mailings about upload/update statuses can be automated
FR-5.2	Back-end	Reporting	Log	The log keeps track of errors	E.g. 404 errors for links included in the record		Should		WP6 Leader	
FRONT-END										
R6 Interface										
FR-6.1	Front-end	Interface	Language	The interface language is in English	Interface language is in English, but the infrastructure must support extension to multiple interface languages in the future		Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-6.2	Front-end	Interface	Terms-of-use	A user has to accept the terms-of-use	In order to be able to specify what they are signing up to, what will be done to their data etc.		Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-6.3	Front-end	Interface	Feedback	A link to the feedback form for reporting issues and questions is provided	Visible in every view		Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-6.4	Front-end	Interface	Documentation	A link to a documentation/search tips page is provided	Visible in every view		Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-6.5	Front-end	Interface	About	A link to an about page is provided	Visible in every view		Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-6.6	Front-end	Interface	ReIReS branding	A link to the ReIReS website is provided	Visible in every view		Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-6.7	Front-end	Interface	Home	A home button is provided	Visible in every view		Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-6.8	Front-end	Interface	Font size	Change font size	Button to maximize - minimize font-size. Visible in every view. OR Include information on how to use Ctrl+/- in manual		Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-6.9	Front-end	Interface	Breadcrumb	Show/hide breadcrumb	Breadcrumb allows the user to keep track of their location within the platform. Only relevant in hierarchically organized dataset		Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-6.10	Front-end	Interface	Version info	Show when the records were last updated in ReIReS	Visible on record detail page		Must		WP6 Leader	

R7 User Account										
FR-7.1	Front-end	User account	User registration	A user can register an account	Registration of user name, e-mail, agree to the terms of use. Registration function visible in the top-navigation.		Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-7.2	Front-end	User account	Sign-in/Sign-out	A user can sign-in and sign-out of his/her account	Signed in users get access to additional functions such as save favorite queries, create and manage sets, view search history. Sign-in/Sign-out function visible in top navigation	R7.1	Should		WP6 Leader	
FR-7.3	Front-end	User account	Delete account	A user can delete his/her account	Supports 'Right to be forgotten' (GDPR compliant)	R7.2	Should		WP6 Leader	
FR-7.4	Front-end	User account	Account settings	Users should be able to view and edit their profiles by signing in	Users should be able to change profile, preferences, privacy settings ...		Must	"As a registered user I want to change password and my profile so that I can always access to platform and describe my competencies and skills"	WP6 contributors	Use case CNR
FR-7.5	Front-end	User account	Account information	Personal information of users should be stored in accordance with GDPR			Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-7.6	Front-end	Access	Access Management	User account information is provided to endpoint to be able to control access to specific datasets based on IP address	User-identification based on IP so that data provider endpoint can authenticate and authorize access to non-public datasets		Must	"As endpoint I want to receive user-identification data (api-key/ip/pwd/...) so that authenticate and authorize"	WP6 contributors	Use case Brepols (For API to authorize user(type).
FR-7.7	Front-end	Access	Access Management	Authenticate access to specific datasets by identifying a user according to details of his account	E.g. based on IP range, organization email domain (@kuleuven.be), additional key added to profile.. If user does not have authentication, show locked results in UI and a link to access rights.		Could	"As publisher I want to determine visibility of information per user profile so that I can server different data views to different user types."	WP6 contributors	Use case Brepols (Maybe API can self handle this, but deposit may not. There may be different access rights within the same dataset!). Remark: different access rights within same dataset must be handled by data provider API. In case of deposit this seems to be an impossible task to handle. To be further discussed/defined.
FR-7.8	Front-end	User account	Single Sign-on	User can link their account to that of their institution	Less user names and passwords to remember		Won't	"As a researcher I want to use an institutional single sign-on (Shibboleth) in order to access to my account in ReIReS platform so that I do not need to create a new ReIReS account, I can use my institutional authentication."	WP6 contributors	Use case EPHE. Remark: Authorization and access control is out of scope for this project but should be considered for follow-up projects.
R8 Reuse of Data										
FR-8.1	Front-end	Reuse	Reference/Share	A citation function is available for each record	Different citation models (e.g. APA, Harvard 1) are provided. Copy the citation to clipboard is available.		Should	"As a researcher I want a tool to export citations of records so that I can efficiently add records to my research bibliography"	WP6 Leader	
FR-8.2	Front-end	Reuse	Reference/Share	A user can share a reference to a record on social media	Social buttons 'Addthis', including Email (http://www.addthis.com/social-buttons). GDPR compliant.		Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-8.3	Front-end	Reuse	Reference/Share	A user can share a reference to a search result on social media	Search links should be persistent. GDPR compliant.		Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-8.4	Front-end	Reuse	Reference/Share	A user can copy a permalink of the record	A persistent resolvable URI can yield a hyperlink that is less susceptible to link rot		Must	"As a researcher I want to obtain a persistent identifier of a resource so that I can quote the resource in a paper or online publication."	WP6 contributors	Use case EPHE
FR-8.5	Front-end	Reuse	Reference/Share	A user can copy a permalink for a set made on his/her profile	Provide a link to the set a user makes on his profile	8.10	Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-8.6	Front-end	Reuse	Download/Export/Print	A user can print a search result or set (basic metadata) as a PDF	Limited to 20 items per page?		Could	"As all user I want to access and download metadata so that I can steer my research"	WP6 contributors	Use case CNR
FR-8.7	Front-end	Reuse	Download/Export/Print	A user can export a search result or set (basic metadata) as JSON (ReIReS model), RIS, BibTex, Endnote, CSV file	From search result provides individual or page toggle selection, from set gives all records in set.		Could	"As a researcher I want to export a data (or search results) in a reference management software (Zotero, EndNote, etc.) so that I can manage the references for my own research"	WP6 Leader	
FR-8.8	Front-end	Reuse	Download/Export/Print	A user can download a single record as a PDF			Could	"As a researcher I want to be able to print or download or send by mail results and full texts so that I consult these offline"	WP6 contributors	Use Apeldoorn, CNR. Remark: Full texts will not necessarily be part of the ReIReS database. It is in first place a discovery system leading to resources (incl. full texts) hosted on other platforms.
FR-8.9	Front-end	Reuse	Download/Export/Print	A user can export a single record as a JSON (ReIReS model), RIS, BibTex, Endnote, CSV file	From search result provides individual or page toggle selection, from set gives all records in set.		Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-8.10	Front-end	Reuse	Collect	A registered user can add records to a new or existing set on his/her profile	A user can select records (toggle check or all results) from search results and add them to a new or existing set. A user can add a single record (from record view page) to an existing or new set.	7.1	Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-8.11	Front-end	Reuse	Favorites	A registered user can view and manage his/her set	A registered user can view all records in a set, can change the set title, can delete (toggle check) records from the set.	8.10	Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-8.12	Front-end	Reuse	Favorites	A registered user can add personal tags/keywords to saved records	Tags private to user (public tags would require monitoring/validation)?		Could		WP6 Leader	

FR-8.13	Front-end	Reuse	Favorites	A registered user can view and reuse saved queries	Users can repeat queries at a later date or review their methodology		Should	"As researcher I want to make a search and history builder and save this so that I do not miss results"	WP6 contributors	Use case Apeldoorn
FR-8.14	Front-end	Reuse	Favorites	A registered user can view his/her search history on session level			Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-8.15	Front-end	Reuse	Infrastructure	Users can use the platform to make presentations/exhibitions with the material in the database	A functionality is provided whereby records from the dataset can be showcased		Won't	"As an institution I want the option to provide a platform with workflows, databases, technical possibilities presenting as well institutions as their content, databases. so that I can reuse infrastructure, workflows of similar projects, e.g.	WP6 contributors	Use case JGU Mainz. Remark: such an infrastructure, to support partners in building their own infrastructure/subsites/exhibits is not in scope
FR-8.16	Front-end	Reuse	Full-text	Users are able to add comments in machine readable full text records on- and offline	A viewer that allows an overlay to digital representations of records so users can work with the text		Won't	"As a researcher I want to insert in a off-line mode my commentaries to texts which are on line so that when I read on-line texts my computer displays and merge the my comments and the source I am studying"	WP6 contributors	Use case FSCIRE. Remark: The ReIReS discovery platform does not harvest digital representations. It only harvests and makes discoverable the metadata which will include a link to the digital images as hosted on the providers site. Annotation tools are out of scope of the environment.
FR-8.17	Front-end	Reuse	Distribution	ReIReS data is connected to and discoverable via Worldcat			Won't	ReIReS data is connected to and discoverable via Worldcat	WP6 contributors	Use case Apeldoorn. Remark: This is out of scope for the project, mainly because the use of Worldcat (service data and reuse data via API) is a paying service. It would require multiple investments not foreseen within the budget of the project.
R9 Analytics										
FR-9.1	Front-end	Analytics	User action logging	The infrastructure keeps track of user actions for statistics/analytics	Should be respectful of GDPR regulations		Must	"As an institution I want to obtain analytics, statistics and analytics (number of users, search keywords) of the resources that I provide to ReIReS so that The research institution or laboratory can produce easily the reports about the use of data that they provide to ReIReS. "as publisher/institution I want to collect statistics on (dataset/platform) usage so that I can provide feedback to institutions on platform/dataset usage." "As platform admin I want to assess result scoring of the datasets so that I can	WP6 contributors	Use case EPHE, Brepols
R10 Search										
FR-10.1	Front-end	Search	Simple search	Simple search on all metadata	Simple search on a word or a phrase. Support auto-suggest value.		Must	"As a researcher I want To search in ReIReS Database threw library engines so that I can find the resources threw the library search engine"	WP6 contributors	Use case EPHE
FR-10.2	Front-end	Search	Facets	Facets for further filtering of search results options on specific metadata	After a simple or advanced search a user gets additional facet filter options for refining the results. Per facet multiple filters can be selected. Selected filters can be applied, filter can be removed one by one, all filters can be cleared at once. Selection to be based on ReIReS data model.		Must	"As a researcher I want to have clear search filters so that I find specific results "	WP6 contributors	Use case Apeldoorn, CNR, JGU
FR-10.3	Front-end	Search	Browse	Browse on facet	Immediate browse on facet without initial search. Possible browse facet filters: data provider dataset, type	10.2	Must	"As a researcher I want the possibility to search subject headings linked to different international / national normed data / thesauri so that I can search for a certain subject heading in all databases" "As a student I want to browse search a specific collection so that I can see what type of collection is"	WP6 contributors	Use case JGU, CNR (i.e. show titles and metadata of any level of collections. Show a description of the collection). Remark: No collection description will be added. Data providers do not have these kind of collection records. browsing on data provider and dataset name will be possible however.
FR-10.4	Front-end	Search	Advanced search	Advanced search on any field and with AND/OR/NOT operators	Any field - contains words/contains phrase/starts with - search term(s) AND/OR/NOT - any field - contains words/contains phrase/starts with - search term(s) More lines can be added. Search can be cleared.		Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-10.5	Front-end	Search	Simple search	Simple search	AND/OR/NOT are recognized in simple search		Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-10.6	Front-end	Search	Search	Support for search with wildcard	e.g. * or ? To replace characters		Could		WP6 Leader	

FR-10.7	Front-end	Search	Save query	A registered user can save queries for later reuse	The saved query is added in the favorites overview.	7.1	Should	"As a researcher I want the option to save queries so that I can regularly check for new records related to my research"	WP6 Leader	
FR-10.8	Front-end	Search	Save query	E-mail alerts for new results for a saved query	Updates to the database would yield new results, e-mail alerts mean not having to check the database periodically		Won't	"As a researcher I want To select keywords and receive a notification when a new data related to the selected keywords is added so that I can be informed about the new data about my field of research."	WP6 contributors	Use case EPHE. Remark: Nice idea for a later project
FR-10.9	Front-end	Search	Transliteration	Platform recognizes transliteration of different scripts	Mapping of different scripts to Latin alphabet is needed		Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-10.10	Front-end	Search	Virtual keyboard	Virtual keyboard	Virtual keyboard to easily switch to Hebrew, Greek... Support RTL (right-to-left) typing for Hebrew and other RTL written text		Should		WP6 Leader	E.g. http://www.hebrewbooks.org/home.aspx
FR-10.11	Front-end	Search	Hits	Show number of hits	Number of hits in search result overview, number of hits on specific filter.		Should		WP6 Leader	
FR-10.12	Front-end	Search	Full-text	Search options include machine readable full text search			Could		WP6 Leader	Remark: only useful when machine readable full text is delivered by data provider
FR-10.13	Front-end	Search	Search matching	Auto-complete for names and titles	To offer some guidance to users, considering different ways of writing names or terminology in different languages		Could	"As a researcher I want auto-complete while searching records so that queries are suggested when I am unsure about spelling"	WP6 Leader	
FR-10.14	Front-end	Search	Advanced search	Authority list search	Searching on controlled authority lists (e.g. VIAF name, Geonames place name...).	R2.3	Could	"As a researchers I want the possibility to search persons linked to different international/national normed data / thesauri so that I can search for a certain person in all databases"	WP6 contributors	Use case JGU Mainz
FR-10.15	Front-end	Search	Search matching	Fuzzy search/approximate string matching	Queries also give results that match them approximately (e.g. Did you mean...?)		Could		WP6 Leader	
R11 Search Results										
FR-11.1	Front-end	Search results	Overview	Basic metadata is shown in search result overview	Thumbnail image if available / Icon if type is known, title, type, data provider, online accessible,... Selection to be based on ReIReS data model.		Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-11.2	Front-end	Search results	Overview	Users see why the results are relevant to their query when possible	Matching term is highlighted in search result overview		Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-11.3	Front-end	Search results	Sorting	Search results can be sorted	By relevance, by title, by available with online resource, by newest/most recently added, by type, by subject...		Should	As a researcher I want to sort query results so that I can arrange them according to oldest or newest"	WP6 Leader	A standardized order of diacritic marks must be worked out
FR-11.4	Front-end	Search results	Grouping	Search results can be grouped together	Facets not only allow the user to filter results, but also to group them by e.g. author, place,...		Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-11.5	Front-end	Search results	Pagination	Support of pagination/load more results in case of large number of results	Pagination/load more results/simultaneous scrolling to be supported in case of large number of results.		Should		WP6 Leader	
FR-11.6	Front-end	Search results	Overview	Hit-highlighting in machine readable full text search	Return the entire document or an excerpt and point out the words or phrases that match the query	R2.9	Could	"As a researcher I want to locate on a page (pdf) the exact beginning/end of an indirect quotation so that we can immediately recognize the border between source and commentary/use of the source"	WP6 contributors	Use case FSCIRE. Remark: can only be done when full text document is delivered with dataset upload by the data provider.

R12 Record View										
FR-12.1	Front-end	Record view	Record	Metadata and link to online version	Only when user has access to the dataset. In case of paid access dataset, IP access control will happen and user will receive a message that access to the full metadata requires a subscription (link to provider site).	R7.5	Must		WP6 Leader	
FR-12.2	Front-end	Record view	Similar items	Similar items are shown	Similar items are shown based on parameters such as keyword, subject, author...		Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-12.3	Front-end	Record view	Previous/Next item	A user can go to the previous/next item of his search results			Should		WP6 Leader	
FR-12.4	Front-end	Record view	Reuse	License and rights information clearly published and visible in each record	License and rights added either at ingest on dataset level or in metadata on record level.	R1.1	Must	"As a publisher I want clearly visible license agreements so that the users know how they can use the image"	WP6 Leader	
FR-12.5	Front-end	Record view	Related	Show more related metadata in database	Show more button launches query on similar metadata: E.g. search more from this author, search more for this subject... Match will not always be 100% since author names will not be controlled.		Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-12.6	Front-end	Record view	Related	Show enrichments	Show enrichments button gives overview of enrichments with links to follow (e.g. VIAF, Geonames)	R2.3	Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-12.7	Front-end	Record view	Browsing	Support of machine readable full text navigation options	Go to page x in full text/zoom in-out/search in full text/...	R2.9	Could		WP6 Leader	
FR-12.8	Front-end	Record view	Related	Connecting primary and secondary sources	i.e. ancient texts and the commentaries written about said texts		Won't	"As a collection expert / a researcher I want to connect words/concepts of the texts of my database with bibliography records of a library catalogue so that we have a tool to connect primary and secondary sources"	WP6 contributors	Use case FSCIRE. Remark: Out of scope since the front-end is a discovery environment and not a management/enrichment environment. In some way this could be possible, but only by mapping different concepts from controlled lists/vocabularies/thesauri together (see requirement R2.4).
FR-12.9	Front-end	Record view	Record linking	Records related to the same source/name/concept include links to one and other	Related records are brought together in a hyperlink network		Won't	"As a collection expert/a researcher I want to connect several documents of my database so that when I come across a particular source/name/concept which occurs elsewhere in the corpus of texts I have uploaded, I can have an immediate 'map' of all the occurrences"	WP6 contributors	Use case FSCIRE. Remark: Out of scope since the front-end is a discovery environment and not a management/enrichment environment. In some way this could be possible, but only by mapping different concepts from controlled lists/vocabularies/thesauri together (see requirement R2.4).
FR-12.10	Front-end	Record view	Browsing	A link to the original record at the data provider's location is provided in each record	A record can be easily traced to the source it was aggregated/federated from. Only in the case when an online webresource is available.		Must	"As end user I want to click through to the native dataset-record so that I can see the full record in its native context"	WP6 contributors	Use case Brepols
FR-12.11	Front-end	Record view	Browsing	A link that allows a query to be repeated in the native dataset	When clicking through to the native dataset, all results for the query leading there are shown		Won't	"As end user I want to click through to repeat the search in the native-dataset so that I can see the full result list within a specific dataset, and drill up/down"	WP6 contributors	Use case Brepols - e.g. walk found manuscript results in the native database. Or further drill down the search in the target database". Remark: a link to the providers site will only be shown on record level. The query in itself can not be matched to the original system anyway since the ReIReS data model will be completely different from the data providers model.

N°	Where	Requirement	Subcategory	Requirement	Use case	Provided by
NFR-1	Back-end	Performance	Response time	The time the system takes to react to input		
NFR-2	Back-end	Performance	Throughput	The maximum rate of processing		
NFR-3	Back-end	Performance	Efficiency	Efficient resource usage for specific performance requirements		
NFR-4	Back-end	Scalability	Traffic	Number of organizations and users		
NFR-5	Back-end	Scalability	Resource allocation	Ease of resource allocation to accommodate changing load		
NFR-6	Back-end	Availability and Recoverability	Performance	Monitor the ability to maintain an accepted level of performance over time		
NFR-7	Back-end	Availability and Recoverability	Errors	Recovery from errors		
NFR-8	Back-end	Data Security and Integrity	GDPR compliancy	Data is handled conforming to GDPR guidelines		
NFR-9	Back-end	Usability	Efficiency	The system functions efficiently for users		
NFR-10	Back-end	API	API endpoint	API access can be put on hold	"As endpoint I want to put and API access on hold so that I can perform maintenance / downtime on the endpoint"	Brepols
NFR-11	Back-end	Interoperability	Technical interoperability	Use services from and provide services to other systems		
NFR-12	Front-end	Interface	User friendly	The interface gives a clear overview of available functions and data		
NFR-13	Front-end	Interface	ReIReS branding	ReIReS design principles are used for ReIReS discovery platform design		
NFR-14	Front-end	Interface	Language	Infrastructure must support extension to multiple interface languages		
NFR-15	Front-end	Interface	Design framework	Responsive design		
NFR-16	Front-end	Usability	Documentation	A documentation/search tips page is provided to guide new users		
NFR-17	Front-end	Usability	Ease to learn	The design of the interface and related documentation aim for a fast learning curve		
NFR-18	Front-end	Usability	Satisfying for a target user community	The platform is designed with its users in mind		

Annex 8. Glossary

Term	Definition
Baseline	A significant state within the revision history of any configuration item
Best Practice	Proven Activities or Processes that have been successfully used by multiple Organisations.
Blocking problem	A problem for which no workaround solution is available at the time of the discovery and which prevents the normal use of the product or of a main functionality
Change management	The process responsible of controlling and tracking changes to artefacts.
Change Request (CR)	A general term for any request from a stakeholder to change an artefact or process. A change request can be an Enhancement Requests or a Defect
DG RESEARCH	Direction Générale de la Recherche
Escalation	Process that pass information and/or requesting action on an incident, problem or change to more senior staff (hierarchical escalation)
Grant Agreement	Contract signed between the Commission and REIRES for the provision of IT services for the development, maintenance, training, user guidance and support of DG RESEARCH information systems, and for support, user guidance, and training of Office Automation and Commission Corporate information systems
Incident	An unplanned interruption to an IT Service or a reduction in the Quality of an IT Service. Failure of a Configuration Item that has not yet impacted Service is also an Incident. For example Failure of one disk from a mirror set.
Information System	A system, whether automated or manual, that comprises people, machines, and/or methods organised to collect, process, transmit, and disseminate data that represent intermediate of final outputs of business processes.
Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	A Metric that is used to help manage a Process, IT Service or Activity. Many Metrics may be measured, but only the most important of these are defined as KPIs and used to actively manage and report on the Process, IT Service or Activity. KPIs should be selected to ensure that Efficiency, Effectiveness, and Cost Effectiveness are all controlled.
Monthly Progress Report (MPR)	Report provided every month containing all necessary information to follow-up the Grant execution
Post Implementation review (CI)	CI is a comprehensive feedback process designed to assess project outcomes and performance. This assessment focuses on how well the project outcomes were matched to the actual needs that the project aimed to fulfil.

Problem	A cause of one or more Incidents
Process	Sequence of activities designed to accomplish a specific objective. A Process takes one or more defined inputs and turns them into defined outputs. A Process defines roles, responsibilities, tasks, tools, standards and management controls required.
Repository	A storage place for work products (artefacts) output during process enactment, such as requirements, results (i.e. metrics), object models, interfaces, and implementations.
Review	Activity carried out to discover potential defects and to assess the quality of a set of artefacts.
Risk	A possible Event that could cause harm or loss, or affect the ability to achieve Objectives. A Risk is measured by the probability of a Threat, the Vulnerability of the Asset to that Threat, and the Impact it would have if it occurred.
Risk Management	The Process responsible for identifying, assessing and controlling Risks.
Service	A means of delivering value to Customers by creating Outcomes Customers want to achieve without the ownership of specific Costs and Risks.
Service Level	Measured and reported achievement against one or more Service Level Targets. The term Service Level is sometimes used informally to mean Service Level Target.
Performance Indicators (PI)	Agreement between REIRES and the Commission specifying, in measurable terms, the service levels to be provided to the Commission.
System	Integrated software composed of diverse, interacting, and specialised, components, structures and functions that work together to realise an objective that meets user needs.
Team leader	The team leader is the interface between project management and developers. The team leader is responsible for ensuring that a task is allocated and monitored to completion. The team leader is responsible for ensuring that development staff follow project standards, and adhere to project schedules.

ReIReS

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